

Assessment of Factors Affecting Academic Achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study sought to investigate the assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of secondary school female students in Okigwe Local Government Area Of Imo State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study design was descriptive survey. The population for the study is 3,560 which consisted of all female secondary school students in public schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State. The sample size is 180 students. Out of the 9 public secondary schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, 4 were chosen by simple random sampling. Furthermore, 45 students were selected from the 4 public secondary schools. The questionnaire titled: Assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students (AFAAASSFS). It was constructed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, Section A sought to find out the bio-data of the respondents, section B is divided into two parts based on the research questions. The coefficient of reliability has been estimated at 0.81 which was suitable for the studies. Item mean was used to answer the research questions, any item above 2.5 is considered accepted and below 2.5 is rejected. T-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant levels. Finding from the study revealed that that a lot of factors affect the academic achievement of female secondary school students. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which make the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. It was recommended that school counsellors should invite and visit parents regularly to foster their interest in children education.

Keywords: Assessment, Factors, Academic Achievement Female Students

Introduction

Academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity. There is a strong link between academic achievement and socio – economic development of the members of the society. It is the outcome of education – the extent to which a student has learned (Adeyemi & Adeyemi, 2014). Okolo et. al. (2017) observed that some students often complain that ‘other student(s) perform better than themselves because the former is better inclined’ while both were taught in the same environment with same teaching method, same content, same time, by the same person and under the same condition. In the same sets of students, one finds the geniuses as well as the dummies. While the geniuses make positive impact in the society, the dummies go about constituting nuisance both to himself, immediate community and the entire society at large.

Academic achievement determines the extent to which the teachers and school leaders are successful in terms of their pedagogical and management processes and practices (Razu & Afrin, 2018). Academic success and accomplishments can be measured by how well students perform on exams and tests. Furthermore, according to Farooq, et. al. (2011), academic achievement of students is the main priority of all educators. There would be no schools, students, lecturers, supporting personnel, instructional resources to improve teaching, examinations and tests to gauge student’s comprehension of pedagogy and competencies if there is no assessment of students’ academic achievement.

Assessment of learning becomes critical in post primary education because a look into educational institutions of learning reveals that students who perform poorly in academics are occasionally admitted, promoted and allowed into higher classes (Asuquo & Chuktu, 2016), which should not be permitted in an ideal society, because it adds to the complication and ambiguity of dealing with issues related to students learning and evaluating their academic performance at secondary institutions. As a result, coping with the challenges of students learning and assessing their academic achievement becomes more difficult at secondary education.

The stakeholders’ major concern in education is poor performance. This is because it leads to tragic wastage of human, social and economic potentials of countries worldwide. Many factors such as lack of facilities in schools, lack of teachers, indiscipline, unfavorable home environment, absenteeism and repetition, low intelligence and anxiety do cause poor academic achievement (Ndirangu, 2007). Demeke and Ashagrie (2017) observed that age, gender and socio-economic background were

responsible for differences in academic achievement. It was also observed that negative attitude of both male and female teachers towards female students affect their ability to perform well in various subjects (Aragaw, 2016), and the quality of teachers has a greater impact on girls' education than boys. On the other hand, tasks like homework, tutoring, punishment, sex ratio, and class size have slightly different effects on girls than boys (Mensch & Lloyd, 2008).

Furthermore, Zewude and Aashine (2016) attempted to assess and identify the major factors or independent variables that influence student academic performance at the College of Natural and Computation Science of Wolaita Sodo University in Ethiopia using binary logistic regression. The study revealed that peer influence, securing the first choice of department, arranging study time outside class, amount of money received from family and father's education level were significant variables that influenced academic performance of students in the school.

Muhammed, and Jibril (2019) researched on the examination of students' family socio-economic status as well as availability of academic facilities as it affects students' academic achievement in the department of statistics, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was conducted on a sample of 100 students from the department. Data for the research was obtained through a structured questionnaire with a response value of 90 students. Regression Analysis and Analysis of Variance of the determined model indicated a strong positive relationship between CGPA and the predictors. The result of the analysis indicated that availability of reading materials, interest in course of study and reading habits contributed to students' academic performance determined by CGPA.

Reports presented by Tokunbo et. al. (2018)] indicated that, despite effective communication skills, subject mastery and proper class room management on the side of lecturers, students' academic achievement was deterred by unwanted pregnancy, poor water and electricity supply, inadequate social interaction avenue, poor staff offices as well as hostels. Furthermore, Chi-Square analysis revealed relationship between other factors like socio-economic status, family background and availability of academic facilities, which contributed to the performance of students at various Colleges of Education. It was recommended that parental support to students and funding of Colleges of education is pertinent to students' performance at such tertiary institutions. A descriptive method was adopted by Okoedion et. al. (2019) where stratified data, which ensures gender balance, was collected. Analysis using percentages, means, t-test and multiple regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was employed to determine academic performance of students in Nigerian Universities from a sample size of 400. Findings indicated that the major factors affecting students' academic performance in Nigerian universities are student, lecturer and institutional related factors. The study also revealed a significant joint contribution of student, lecturer, institutional and home-related factors on poor academic performance of students in Nigerian universities. Conclusion and recommendations were provided in the light of the empirical findings. It is therefore based on the above phenomena that this study is specifically designed to assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

In a nutshell, students act or behave in a very funny way, one wonders if all students came to study or not. There is high rate of examination malpractice, non-chalant attitude towards class work, chatting with online friends while lectures are going on, playing and listening to music in class, coming to class late and sometimes do not even attend or appear in class till the examination day, pays little or no attention to study materials, high rate of carry over courses, causing problems for the serious students, the lecturers and the school system at large. It is therefore based on the above phenomena that this study is specifically designed to assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the Factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. The interest of the researchers is to assess critically and identify the factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives include to Identify:

1. Factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.
2. Solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What is the item mean factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?

2. What is the item mean of solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the item mean of junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted was descriptive survey. It is a precursor to quantitative research designs as it provides the general overview, giving some valuable pointers as to what variables are worth testing quantitatively. The population for the study is 3,560 which consisted of all female secondary school students in public schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State. The sample size is 180 students. Out of the 9 public secondary schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, 4 were chosen by simple random sampling. Furthermore, 45 students were selected from the 4 public secondary schools.

Research Instruments

The major research instrument(s) adopted in the study was the questionnaire titled: Assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students (AFAAASSFS). It was constructed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, Section A sought to find out the bio-data of the respondents, section B is divided into two parts based on the research questions. The four-point scale of strongly agreed [SA] 4 points, agreed [A] 3 points, disagreed [D] 2 points, and Strongly Disagreed [SD] 1point were used to rate the reaction of the respondents to the items contained in the questionnaires. 2.5 weighted marks was used to assess the outcome of the analysis.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The researchers constructed the questionnaire and gave it to research experts in the Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria to determine the validity. Professional corrections and comments were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument to ensure that it had content validity. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, pilot study was conducted by administering it on a sample of 30 respondents in Onuimo Local Government Area of Imo State, which was not part of the original sample population. The exercise was repeated in two weeks interval and the data from both tests were analysed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The coefficient of reliability has been estimated at 0.81 which was suitable for the studies.

Method of Data Collection

The research instrument was administered and collected from the respondents by the researcher. After the distribution of the questionnaire, respondents were given a week to fill out the questionnaire. This time frame was given in order to give enough time to the respondents to reflect on the items on the questionnaire and ensure valid responses. All the 180 copies of the questionnaires were administered to the respondents, all the questionnaire were retrieved.

Method of Data Analysis

Item mean was used to answer the research questions, any item above 2.5 is considered accepted and below 2.5 is rejected. T-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant levels.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the item mean of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria? Present the statistical data analysis used to answer the research question 1 in table as shown below:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State.

S/N	factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	School location	180	581.00	3.11	.74	Agreed
2.	Parental education	180	591.00	3.18	.64	Agreed
3.	Parental economic status	180	591.00	3.16	.68	Agreed
4.	Parental social class	180	587.00	3.14	.59	Agreed
5.	Parental income	180	609.00	3.26	.57	Agreed
6.	Peer pressure	180	595.00	3.12	.60	Agreed

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7. Youthful disposition	180	613.00	3.28	.59	Agreed
8. Early marriage	180	571.00	3.05	.68	Agreed
9. School phobia	180	519.00	2.78	.83	Agreed
10. Environmental factors	180	513.00	2.74	.87	Agreed
11. Child labour	180	555.00	2.97	.74	Agreed
12. Single parent homes	180	589.00	3.15	.57	Agreed
13. Poverty	180	575.00	3.07	.64	Agreed
14. Religious belief	180	525.00	2.81	.83	Agreed
15. First child in the family	180	535.00	2.86	.79	Agreed
16. Parental indiscipline status	180	497.00	2.66	.89	Agreed
17. Cultural beliefs	180	479.00	2.56	.79	Agreed
18. Fear of academic failure	180	481.00	2.57	.78	Agreed
19. Gender preference	180	479.00	2.56	.73	Agreed
20. Unwanted pregnancy	180	636.00	3.40	.79	Agreed
TOTAL	180	5,56	2.97	0.72	Agreed

Field 2023

Table 1 revealed the responses of student to factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State. Item 20 have the highest mean of 3.40 which pointed out the Unwanted pregnancy is core factor that affect female secondary school student academic achievement while item 17: Cultural beliefs and 19: Gender preference both with mean of 2.56 were considered as least factors that affect female students' academic achievement. All the 20 items were accepted as factors that affect female students' academic achievement.

Research Question 2

What is the item mean of solution academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State.

S/N	Statistics solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students	N				Remark
			Sum	Mean	SD	
1.	Establishment of school's nearness to the people	180	621.00	3.32	.74	Agreed
2.	Parental motivation for females	180	641.00	3.43	.74	Agreed
3.	Providing academic materials for students	180	628.00	3.36	.72	Agreed
4.	Encouraging female children to imitate good models	180	638.00	3.41	.70	Agreed
5.	Proper discipline of children	180	631.00	3.37	.78	Agreed
6.	Good upbringing	180	622.00	3.33	.75	Agreed
7.	Youthful disposition	180	605.00	3.26	.78	Agreed
8.	Preventing early marriage for female children	180	647.00	3.46	.65	Agreed
9.	Ensuring gender equality	180	619.00	3.31	.76	Agreed
10.	Improvement of school environment	180	626.00	3.35	.70	Agreed
	Total	180	6278	3.36	0.73	Agreed

Field 2023

Table 2 revealed the responses of student to solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State. Item 8: Preventing early marriage for female children have the highest mean of 3.46 and item 7: Youthful disposition with the least mean of 3.26. all the 10 items were considered acceptable.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: T-test Statistics on the difference the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Junior female in JSS	101	1.29	.45449	.04373	178	1.134	0.135
Senior Female in SSS	79	1.38	.48842	.05495			

Field 2023

The result in Table 3 revealed a t-test statistic on the difference the item means junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State at $t(1.134)$, $df=178$, $P>0.05$. The Hypothesis is accepted. The implication is that There is a significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question one revealed that a lot of factors affect the academic achievement of female secondary school students. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which make the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. More so, Cultural beliefs and Gender preference was also a listed factor that have negated the academic achievement of the female students. In some culture it is seen as taboo to send the girl to further her education and male children are given more preference. This finding is in line with Demeke and Ashagrie (2017) observed that age, gender and socio-economic background were responsible for differences in academic achievement. The works of Tokunbo et. al. (2018) affirmed this finding that, despite effective communication skills, subject mastery and proper class room management on the side of lecturers, students' academic achievement was deterred by unwanted pregnancy, poor water and electricity supply, inadequate social interaction avenue, poor staff offices as well as hostels. The hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students.

Finding from the other research question revealed solutions to the factors affecting secondary school female students academic achievement can be solved. One of such way is the prevention of early marriage of the female students, so as not to have negative impact on their academic achievement. Other possible solution to the identified factors, which are establishment of school's nearness to the people, parental motivation for females, and encouraging female children to imitate good models. This is in line with Muhammed, and Jibril (2019) that parental role in adolescents education have a lot of positive impact on their academic achievement.

Implication of the findings of Study to Counsellors

The outcome of the study would help school counsellors to be equipped with the assessment of factor affecting academic achievement of female student. Programs and activities will be put in place to occupy the time of female students not to get involved in what will hamper their academic achievement.

Conclusion

This study examined assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which makes the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. Cultural beliefs and Gender preference were also listed factors that have negated the academic achievement of the female students. One of such ways is the prevention of early marriage of female students so as not to have negative impact on their academic achievement. Other possible solutions to the identified factors, are establishment of school's nearness to the people, parental motivation for females, and encouragement of female children to imitate good models.

Recommendations

Recommendations were made based on research findings;

1. Government should vigorously pursue and enlighten the public adequately on the importance of female education.
2. Government should provide the enabling environment for learning. Facilities like laboratories, libraries, sporting equipment, adequate number of teachers etc.

3. Government should provide employment opportunities to enable parents meet their children's academic requirements.
4. School counsellors should invite and visit parents regularly to foster their interest in children education.

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